

New Spray Reagents for the Detection of Hazardous Phenols separated by Tlc

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The separation pattern of 22 phenols have been studied on silica gel-G tlc plates using chloroform-methanol (98 : 2) as developer. The spots were detected using 4 new spray reagents, viz. orthanilic acid, *o*-dianisidine and their diazotised products. Most of the phenols gave easily detectable characteristic colours and the detection limit was generally 1-5 μ g, and even as low as 0.1-0.5 μ g in most case for the diazotised orthanilic acid.

THE urgency of development of rapid and inexpensive methods for the detection of hazardous phenols which often pollute industrial effluents as well as river water¹ even when present in low levels, has promoted the use of various forms of chromatography for this purpose. Though various spray reagents² have been reported for the detection of phenols on tlc plate, none of them has been used for the detection of the phenols frequently encountered in river water.

In this communication we have reported the use of orthanilic acid, *o*-dianisidine and their diazotised products for rapid and efficient detection of 22 such phenols. Though diazotised *o*-dianisidine finds mention in a method of separation and detection of phenols by paper chromatography, all the spray reagents are new introduction in the field of tlc.

Experimental

Spray reagents :

Orthanilic acid : A saturated methanolic solution of the reagent (Fluka, AG) was used.

Diazotised orthanilic acid : Orthanilic acid (0.5 g) was dissolved in 12*N* HCl (4.5 ml) by warming and the solution diluted to 50 ml with distilled water. A 10 ml portion of the solution was mixed with 5% aqueous NaNO₂ solution (10 ml) after cooling at 0°. An aliquot (10 ml) of the resulting solution was mixed with an equal volume of 10% K₂CO₃ before using it as spray reagent.

***o*-Dianisidine :** *o*-Dianisidine (Koch-Light) was purified by crystallisation from ethanol and a saturated solution in methanol was prepared.

Diazotised *o*-dianisidine : The reagent was prepared by dissolving *o*-dianisidine (0.25 g) in 2*N* HCl (1.5 ml) and diluting it to 50 ml with distilled water. An aliquot (10 ml) was mixed with 10% aqueous sodium nitrite solution (10 ml) after cooling it at 0°.

Procedure : Tlc plates (0.1 mm) were prepared using silica gel-G (E.Merck) and a Unoplan apparatus (Shandon, U.K.). The samples were spotted on tlc plates. After development using chloroform-methanol (98 : 2) as mobile phase, the tlc plates were dried in air at room temperature and sprayed uniformly with the reagent. Heating of chromatoplates at 90° for 10 min in an oven was necessary when orthanilic acid and *o*-dianisidine were used as the spray reagents. In case of diazotised *o*-dianisidine, an aqueous 10% K₂CO₃ was first sprayed and then the plates were air-dried.

The developed tlc procedure may be applied to water samples after extraction and pre-concentration of phenols by standard procedures^{1,3}.

Results and Discussion

The observed colours and detection limits for the phenols tested with orthanilic acid and its diazotised product (Table 1) indicate that the sensitivity of the spray reagents are quite high (detection limit, 0.1-5.0 μ g). Various easily distinguishable colours were developed due to the interaction of spray reagents with the phenols immediately after experiment except in the case of 2,4,6-trichlorophenol which required about 45 min for the development of colour. However, a limited number of the phenols produced colours with orthanilic acid while the other could not be detected even when present in amounts upto 50 μ g. For the phenols which gave easily distinguishable colours with this reagent (Table 1), the detection limit is as low as 1.0-5.0 μ g. Only the combination of *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols and *o*-aminophenol are difficult to differentiate using the above reagent.

The diazotised orthanilic acid reagent is capable of showing different colours with all the phenols. But some of the phenols, like phenol, *p*-cresol, *p*-phenylphenol, 2,4- and 2,3-xyleneols, *o*-chlorophenol, *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols, 2,4-dinitrophenol and 4-chloro-*m*-cresol developed same colour (yellow)

TABLE 1—COLOURS DEVELOPED BY PHENOLS USING ORTHANILIC ACID AND DIAZOTISED ORTHANILIC ACID AS SPRAY REAGENTS

Sl. no.	Phenol	Orthanilic acid		Diazotised orthanilic acid		R_f -values in CHCl_3 -MeOH (98 : 2)
		Colour observed	Detection limit (μg)	Colour observed	Detection limit (μg)	
1.	Phenol	—	—	Yellow	0.3	0.84
2.	α -Naphthol	Yellow	2.0	Pink	0.1	0.44
3.	β -Naphthol	Pink	1.0	Orange	0.1	0.87
4.	<i>o</i> -Cresol	—	—	Pink	0.5	0.46
5.	<i>m</i> -Cresol	—	—	Brown	0.5	0.86
6.	<i>p</i> -Cresol	—	—	Yellow	0.5	0.86
7.	<i>o</i> -Aminophenol	Yellow	5.0	Brown	0.1	0.10
8.	<i>p</i> -Aminophenol	Chocolate	5.0	Dark yellow	0.1	Base line
9.	Catechol	Ash	5.0	Straw yellow	0.2	0.08
10.	Thymol	—	—	Brown	0.1	0.61
11.	<i>p</i> -Phenylphenol	—	—	Yellow	1.0	0.99
12.	2,4-Xylenol	—	—	Yellow	0.5	0.48
13.	2,3-Xylenol	—	—	Yellow	0.5	0.47
14.	3,5-Xylenol	Yellow	2.0	Pink	0.5	0.98
15.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenol	—	—	Yellow	5.0	0.59
16.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	—	—	Dark yellow	1.0	0.92
17.	2,4-Dichlorophenol	—	—	Pink	2.5	0.54
18.	2,4,6-Trichlorophenol	—	—	Pale brown*	3.0	0.62
19.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	Yellow	2.0	Yellow	0.5	0.21
20.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	Yellow	2.0	Yellow	0.5	0.20
21.	2,4-Dinitrophenol	Yellow	1.0	Yellow	0.5	0.09
22.	4-Chloro- <i>m</i> -cresol	—	—	Yellow	0.5	0.35

*Colour developed after 45 min.

TABLE 2—COLOURS DEVELOPED BY PHENOLS USING *o*-DIANISIDINE AND DIAZOTISED *o*-DIANISIDINE AS SPRAY REAGENTS

Sl. no.	Phenols	<i>o</i> -Dianisidine		Diazotised <i>o</i> -dianisidine	
		Colour observed	Detection limit (μg)	Colour observed	Detection limit (μg)
1.	Phenol	—	—	Ash	5
2.	α -Naphthol	Light yellow	2	Grey	2
3.	β -Naphthol	Greyish pink	1	Deep violet	1
4.	<i>o</i> -Cresol	—	—	Dark yellow	2
5.	<i>m</i> -Cresol	—	—	Dark yellow	2
6.	<i>p</i> -Cresol	—	—	Yellowish brown	2
7.	2,4-Xylenol	—	—	Brown	2
8.	2,3-Xylenol	—	—	Dark yellow	2
9.	3,5-Xylenol	Light yellow	2	Pinkish yellow	1
10.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenol	—	—	Brown	2
11.	2,4-Dichlorophenol	—	—	Chocolate	4
12.	2,4-Dimethylphenol	—	—	Brownish yellow	1
13.	<i>o</i> -Aminophenol	Grey	1	Yellow ochre	1
14.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	Light pink	2	Light yellow	2
15.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	Chocolate	2	Yellow	1
16.	2,4-Dinitrophenol	Yellow	2	Yellow	2
17.	4-Chloro- <i>m</i> -cresol	—	—	Grey	1
18.	2,4,6-Trichlorophenol	—	—	—	—

with diazotised orthanilic acid. Among these phenols, *p*-cresol, *p*-phenylphenol and 4-chloro-*m*-cresol have R_f values close to each other. Similarly, the pairs 2,4- and 2,3-xylenols as well as *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols have very close R_f values. Except these combinations, all other phenols could be detected in presence of each other. Moreover, in river water though all the 22 phenols may be present, only two or three of them are normally present at a time. Thus the diazotised orthanilic acid in particular is useful for the detection of such phenols using combination of different colours and varying R_f values.

The observed colours and detection limits for the tested phenols using *o*-dianisidine and diazotised

o-dianisidine (Table 2) indicate that the sensitivities of these spray reagents are also quite high (1–5 μg). Various distinctive colours developed immediately due to interaction of the spray reagents with the phenols. The diazotised reagent is capable of showing various colours with all the tested phenols except 2,4,6-trichlorophenol, α - and β -naphthols, aminophenols, nitrophenols give good colours at their low detection limits (1–2 μg) with *o*-dianisidine, phenol, cresols, xylenols (except 3,5-xylenol) and chlorophenols do not response to the colour reaction with *o*-dianisidine (Table 2).

The diazotised products of orthanilic acid and *o*-dianisidine are thus useful for the detection of most of the phenols expected in polluted river water

or industrial effluents. US environmental protection agency permits 1.0 mg dm⁻³ phenolic compounds in domestic water while 5.0 mg dm⁻³ for other waters. Thus the procedure developed will provide a rapid method for the detection of most of these phenols in water.

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References

1. L. BENBERG, "Analysis of Organic Micropollutants in Water", eds. A. BJORSETH and G. ANGELETTI,

- Dordrecht, 1982, p. 286; E. STAHL, "Thin-Layer Chromatography: A Laboratory Handbook", Springer, New York, 1969, pp. 856, 866, 874, 886, 890, 899 and 904; J. SHERMA and L. V. S. HOOD, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1965, **17**, 307; G. M. BARTON, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1965, **20**, 189; K. FINK and R. M. FINK, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1949, **70**, 654; G. M. BARTON, R. S. EVANS and J. A. F. GARDNER, *Nature (London)*, 1959, **170**, 249; R. W. KEITH, D. L. TURNEAU and D. MAHLUM, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1958, **1**, 534; A. STURM and H. N. SCHEJA, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1964, **16**, 194; J. H. FREEMAN, *Anal. Chem.*, 1953, **24**, 955; W. J. BURKE, A. D. POTTER and R. M. PARKHURST, *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, **32**, 727; I. M. HAYS and K. MACEK, "Handbuch der Papier Chromatographie I", G. Fischer, Jena, 1958, p. 743.
2. L. REIO, *Chromatogr. Rev.*, 1961, **3**, 92.
 3. A. SDICA, R. CABRIDENC and C. HENNEQUIN, "Analysis of Organic Micropollutants in Water", eds. A. BJORSETH and G. ANGELETTI, Reidel Publishing, Dordrecht, 1982, pp. 24, 88.